
Quality assurance at the macro level: Comparing the current and previous WoS snapshots

Dimity Stephen, Stephan Stahlschmidt and Paul Donner

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Editor:

German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW) GmbH

Lange Laube 12 | 30159 Hannover | Germany | info@dzhw.eu | www.dzhw.eu

POB 2920 | 30029 Hannover | Germany

phone: +49 511 450670-0 | fax: +49 511 450670-960

Chairman of the Supervisory Board:

Ministerialdirigent Peter Greisler

Scientific Director:

Prof. Dr. Monika Jungbauer-Gans

Managing Director:

Axel Tscherniak

Registration Court:

Amtsgericht Hannover | HRB 6489

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Motivation

The aim of the report is to identify any potential changes in data between or within database versions that may indicate quality issues. To do so it offers:

- a visual comparison
- between time-series over the last 10 years
- stemming from the current and previous KB database snapshots
- on several key indicators
- for national, sectoral and institutional entities.

The DZHW already conducts quality assurance testing at the micro-level for the KB's bibliometric databases before the tables enter the production environment. This testing is invaluable to ensuring tables and variables contain the expected content. This report supplements the current micro-level approach by examining changes in key variables between the latest two iterations of the databases at the macro-level of institutions, sectors, countries, and disciplines.

This report is not an exhaustive analysis of the databases' content, nor does it investigate any anomalies identified in the databases. However, this report probes the core variables fundamental to typical bibliometric analyses, serves as an overview of the current state of the databases, and highlights changes that may indicate issues with data quality that warrant further investigation to understand or rectify. Changes may arise through several means. For instance, the database provider may add or remove journals from indices, change the discipline classification, or change how the classification is applied. The KB may identify new or decommissioned institutions, which can affect publication output for particular disciplines, or countries may implement policies regarding publication practices that can exert a substantial influence on the content published over time. This report aims to provide users of the KB databases with an overview of any potential changes soon after the databases enter the production environment, so that these factors may be considered in analyses.

Set of indicators

The indicators included in the report reflect the core variables in the database that are fundamental to key bibliometric analyses and indicators. We provide context to the selection of variables and what information can be determined from their examination in each of the following sections.

We make two sets of comparisons in this report. For indicators where it is important to consider trends over time, such as whole publication counts, we compare the databases for the 10 years up to the year for which both have complete data. For example, the latest common year with complete data for the `wos_b_202304` and `wos_b_202404` databases is 2022, as data for the absolute latest year in each database are incomplete. Similarly, where citation-based indicators are used, we present the time-series up to the latest common year with complete citation data, which is 2020 for the `wos_b_202304` and `wos_b_202404` databases. This comparison highlights any differences in trends between the databases for the most recent decade.

For other indicators, it is most useful to compare changes between just the most recent years of complete data in each database. For instance, we compare the number of publications per discipline in 2022 from the `wos_b_202304` database against 2023 in the `wos_b_202404` database. Changes between the years are expected given we are comparing two different sets of publications. However, this comparison can also provide insight into structural changes between the database iterations, such as the addition or removal of journals from indices, which may influence indicators

at the macro-level. Such comparisons are also helpful in identifying new or removed institutions or discipline categories. Further, although users will likely use the latest database to produce a complete time-series for new analyses, it is important to understand how additional years of a time-series might differ to existing time-series presented in publications and reports.

Set of entities

We have chosen to compare the databases at the national, sectoral, and institutional levels. The countries chosen are based on those most commonly examined by the DZHW as countries against which it is useful and informative to compare Germany. We also examine the key German sectors: Universities (Uni), Fachhochschulen (FH), Max Planck Gesellschaft (MPG), Fraunhofer Gesellschaft (FHG), Helmholtz Gemeinschaft (HGF), Leibniz Gemeinschaft (WGL), the business sector (Econ), non-university hospitals (Clinic), and combined Ressortforschung-Bund and Ressortforschung-Länder (Gov). The remaining smaller sectors, such as research associations, clubs, and international and foreign organisations are grouped into an “other” category. Individual German institutions are also examined via the KB’s institutional coding for Germany. However, as there are a large number of institutions, we present data only for institutions that have shown substantial changes in the indicator of interest.

Methodological details

We focus primarily on articles and reviews published in journals, as these are the most common documents used in bibliometric analyses. Unless otherwise stated, we examine content indexed in the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE), Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI), and the Arts and Humanities Citation Index (A&HCI) WoS indices. As previously noted, we supply a shortened time-series for citation-based indicators to allow for a 3-year citation window. Wang (2013)¹ determined that at least 3 years is required for publications to reach their maximum number of citations per year, after which point the number of citations are likely representative of the publication’s long-term impact. As such, citation-based indicators include all citations received within the publication year and the subsequent two years.

Whole counting is used throughout the report. Although it is most common to use fractional counting, analysing variables using whole counts will still reveal potential changes in the variables.

Data for disciplines are presented based on the `sc_traditional` or Research Areas (RA) classification. The `sc_traditional` is a fine-grained classification that allows changes in specific disciplines to be analysed. However, as it contains over 250 categories, it is sometimes useful to use a higher level of aggregation to present an overview of the disciplines. As such, we also present some data on the RA classification. The RA consists of six broad groups: Life Sciences, Physical Sciences, Technology, Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities, and Multidisciplinary. These groups are mapped from the `sc_traditional` disciplines based on a concordance supplied by Clarivate Analytics.

This report is automated. Consequently, blank tables may appear in this report, but they are nonetheless informative about the indicator under examination.

¹Wang, J. (2013). Citation time window choice for research impact evaluation. *Scientometrics*, 94(3), 851-872. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-012-0775-9

Analysis

Publication counts: Total, selected countries, German sectors, and Research Areas

The count of items produced by selected entities is the most fundamental bibliometric indicator. Given publication counts form the basis of many indicators, understanding the time-series trend within and between databases can inform expectations about potential changes that may arise in other indicators. In Figure 1 we show the total number of documents of different types indexed in each database version. Notably, documents may be allocated to multiple types. We have allowed for double-counting between types, in that each document is counted toward each type it is assigned to. However, the total counts each document only once. Figures 2 to 4 show the whole counts of articles and reviews published by selected countries and German sectors over the last 10 years and in Figure 5 we show the distribution of publications by RA.

Changes in publication counts over time may reflect changes made by countries, the database provider, and/or administrative decisions. For example, it is expected that the `wos_b_202404` database contains a greater number of publications for the most recent years than the `wos_b_202304` database due to the continued indexing of items by Clarivate Analytics past the annual point in April at which the data is cut to create the KB databases.

Increases in publications over time also result from both the continued growth of the national science systems and WoS' ongoing indexation over time. Sharp increases for a particular country may represent an actual increase in the number of a country's articles published in WoS-indexed journals, such as due to policy decisions, or reflect the recent indexing of region-, country-, or discipline-specific journals. Decreases may reflect the de-indexation of journals in which an entity commonly publishes or the stagnation of a sector, such as due to funding or policy decisions or the de-commissioning of an institution. Substantial deviations between databases or decreases in the current database in recent years may warrant investigation.

A note on early access publications

In the 2023 report, it was identified that items of several types, e.g., article, review, proceedings, were being indexed in WoS as "early access" items for the year in which they first appeared online. In the subsequent year (and database version), their publication year and item type was updated by Clarivate from, e.g., "Article, Early Access" published 2021 to "Article" published 2022. This change appeared in Figures 1 to 5 as higher counts of items in the last common year (2021) in the previous database version than the current version. From version `wos_b_202404`, the KB WoS database now includes a variable to identify early access items. However, because this variable was not available in `wos_b_202304`, the same pattern of higher counts of items appears in 2022 in the following Figures due to the inclusion of early access items in `wos_b_202304`. Also, because each item is counted toward each document type it is classified to, early access items appear in both the "early access" category in Figure 1, as well as the main document type, such as article.

Figure 1: Number of documents in each database over time by type.

Figure 2: Whole counts of articles and reviews by country and database over time, part 1.

Figure 3: Whole counts of articles and reviews by country and database over time, part 2. Please note the panels' different axes.

Figure 4: Whole counts of articles and reviews by German sector and database over time. Please note the panels' different axes.

Figure 5: Whole counts of articles and reviews by RA and database over time.

Journals: Total indexed and the number added or removed

The journals indexed constitute the foundation of the database. Year to year changes in the journals indexed reflect the database provider's curation procedures to introduce new content and remove content no longer meeting indexation criteria. The amount of and changes in content indexed can influence bibliometric indicators, particularly if changes are concentrated in specific disciplines. Figure 6 shows the total number of journals in each database over time, while Figure 7 shows the number of journals added and removed in each RA.

Changes in the journals indexed were identified by matching the titles of all journals indexed in 2022 in the `wos_b_202304` database to those with 2023 content in the `wos_b_202404` database. Titles were used as all journals have titles recorded, while some journals are missing ISSNs. Titles in `wos_b_202304` but not in `wos_b_202404` were considered removed, while titles in `wos_b_202404` but not in `wos_b_202304` were considered added. In total, 178 journals were added and 167 were removed. These data may include a small number of journals that changed titles. Some double-counting of journals between RAs may also occur when a journal maps to two or more RAs.

Figure 6: The number of journals indexed in each database over time.

Figure 7: The number of journals added or removed between 2022 in `wos_b_202304` and 2023 in `wos_b_202404` by RA.

Figure 9: ERs, based on whole counts, by selected country and database over time. The black line is the expected 10% threshold.

Citations: Mean 3-year citations of articles and reviews by discipline

The number of citations a publication could be expected to receive is dependent to an extent on its discipline. As such, we examine here the mean 3-year citations of articles and reviews by discipline. Mean 3-year citations (MC3) are the mean citations publications in each discipline accrued in the first 3 years after publication. We examine here in Figure 10 the last common year in both databases (top panels) to assess the retroactive effects stemming from changes made in the latest database, and the latest complete year in both databases (bottom panels) to assess potential structural changes and updates to the time-series. A greater deviation of disciplines from the central line indicates a greater degree of change in the mean citations of a discipline's items between years. The outlying disciplines from the bottom panels of Figure 10 are shown in Tables 1 and 2, along with disciplines where the previous threshold was zero. We use a threshold of a current MC3 of at least 1 for articles and 3 for reviews to remove disciplines with spurious changes due to low levels of citations.

Figure 10: The MC3 for articles and reviews in each discipline between databases, where colour denotes the number of disciplines with this combination of citations.

Table 1: Articles: Disciplines with a current MC3 of at least 1, where the MC3 decreased by over 20% or increased by over 50% between 2020 in wos_b_202304 and 2021 in wos_b_202404, or the previous MC3 was 0.

Discipline	Previous MC3	Current MC3	No. crrent pubs.	Perc. diff.
Mining & Mineral Processing	7.5	11.9	260	58.1
Medical Ethics	2.7	4.0	55	46.4
Psychology, Psychoanalysis	0.8	1.1	237	38.1
Humanities, Multidisciplinary	1.0	1.4	4236	31.2
Medical Laboratory Technology	7.4	4.9	2711	-33.9
Infectious Diseases	13.0	8.5	11295	-34.9
Virology	14.7	8.9	4840	-39.2
Medicine, General & Internal	14.7	8.9	36384	-39.5

Table 2: Reviews: Disciplines with a current MC3 of at least 3, where the MC3 decreased by over 20% or increased by over 60% between 2020 in wos_b_202304 and 2021 in wos_b_202404, or the previous MC3 was 0.

Discipline	Previous MC3	Current MC3	No. crrent pubs.	Perc. diff.
Literature, British Isles	0.0	1.0	4	Inf
Art	0.7	3.2	12	387.2
Mineralogy	3.1	10.7	7	242.9
Computer Science, Theory & Methods	21.4	72.6	33	240.1
Social Sciences, Mathematical Methods	12.5	29.0	7	132.0
Public Administration	4.5	9.8	13	121.0
Tropical Medicine	1.7	3.4	16	102.5
Business, Finance	9.1	16.6	75	82.7
Statistics & Probability	4.6	8.0	58	74.7
Mathematics	5.0	8.6	73	70.6
Archaeology	4.7	7.9	40	67.4
Materials Science, Ceramics	17.8	29.6	166	66.1
Engineering, Aerospace	14.1	23.2	104	64.0
Engineering, Marine	18.9	15.0	105	-20.3
Architecture	5.8	4.6	18	-20.4
Engineering, Ocean	8.0	6.3	9	-20.8
Nutrition & Dietetics	21.1	16.7	2205	-20.8
Medicine, General & Internal	14.9	11.8	9141	-20.9
Reproductive Biology	12.2	9.6	87	-21.0
Zoology	5.8	4.5	282	-21.6
Obstetrics & Gynecology	10.7	8.3	1399	-22.3
Acoustics	22.0	17.1	215	-22.4
Hematology	15.1	11.7	1093	-22.5
Psychology, Social	12.9	10.0	72	-22.9

Mathematics, Applied	4.6	3.6	98	-22.9
Agricultural Engineering	53.7	41.4	206	-22.9
Engineering, Mechanical	23.1	17.7	301	-23.4
Psychology, Developmental	19.4	14.7	266	-24.1
Audiology & Speech-Language Pathology	9.4	7.1	156	-24.1
Immunology	27.4	20.7	5005	-24.3
Spectroscopy	19.9	15.0	84	-24.6
Geochemistry & Geophysics	18.3	13.6	238	-25.4
Quantum Science & Technology	17.6	13.1	42	-25.5
Water Resources	15.7	11.6	51	-25.9
Humanities, Multidisciplinary	4.1	3.1	70	-26.1
Pediatrics	12.5	9.2	1904	-26.2
Mathematics, Interdisciplinary Applications	12.1	8.9	65	-26.4
Sport Sciences	14.8	10.8	584	-26.9
Transplantation	7.7	5.6	143	-27.0
Mathematical & Computational Biology	16.5	12.0	84	-27.2
Emergency Medicine	8.5	6.1	407	-28.0
Otorhinolaryngology	8.9	6.4	652	-28.0
Critical Care Medicine	19.1	13.6	726	-28.8
Cardiac & Cardiovascular Systems	17.8	12.6	3786	-29.2
Biophysics	26.0	18.4	162	-29.3
Infectious Diseases	24.1	16.9	1458	-29.7
Psychiatry	20.5	14.2	1665	-30.7
Physics, Condensed Matter	25.4	17.6	87	-31.0
Nuclear Science & Technology	12.8	8.7	79	-32.1
Multidisciplinary Sciences	30.3	20.5	1849	-32.5
Demography	7.6	5.1	18	-33.5
Toxicology	19.2	12.6	237	-34.3
Psychology	28.7	18.8	52	-34.7
Social Work	6.9	4.5	49	-34.9
International Relations	5.4	3.4	49	-36.0
Surgery	11.2	6.8	2010	-39.5
Meteorology & Atmospheric Sciences	21.0	12.5	64	-40.6
Physics, Fluids & Plasmas	27.9	16.0	26	-42.7
Virology	32.2	17.7	978	-44.9
Transportation Science & Technology	28.6	15.7	10	-45.1
Operations Research & Management Science	22.1	12.1	24	-45.3
Oceanography	18.7	9.3	164	-50.4
Physics, Particles & Fields	112.0	49.2	12	-56.0
Limnology	14.1	4.4	10	-68.8
Mining & Mineral Processing	34.2	6.0	1	-82.5

Uncited articles and reviews: Percent by selected countries and German sectors

While ERs represent the most highly cited publications and mean citations tell us about what’s average, the percentage of uncited publications can tell us about the entities at the tail end of the citation distribution. When examining uncited publications, we expect to see a decreasing trend in uncited publications over time. This occurs because citation counts are based on the items indexed in each database and so, as the database provider continues to index journals, the likelihood increases that any publication will have been cited by the indexed items. In particular, we would expect that the percentage of uncited publications in the last common year would be lower in the current database than the previous database, as data added in the latest iteration “complete” the incomplete last year of the previous database. An increase in uncited publications in the latest year may reflect processing issues that require investigation. We present in Figures 11 and 12 the percentage of articles and reviews per German sector and selected country that remained uncited 3 years after they were published. Please note, the increase in uncited publications for FHG since 2019 stems from the publication of a large number of ingredient safety assessments by one FHG institution in 2020 and 2021.

Figure 11: The percentage of uncited publications in each database over time by German sector.

Figure 12: The percentage of uncited publications in each database over time by selected countries.

Disciplines: Changes in discipline classification

This section shows in Table 3 any changes that have been made to WoS' sc_traditional classification. This could include splits, aggregations or removals of a discipline, or the inclusion of a new discipline to reflect new and emerging topics. We identify changes in the classification structure by comparing the number of articles and reviews attributed to each discipline in the latest years of each database and selecting those disciplines where the number was zero in one year but not in the other. Disciplines with no prior publications but some in the current year suggest the discipline may have been recently added, while the opposite suggests the discipline may have been removed or merged. Changes may also reflect changes in spelling or punctuation of the discipline name. Any changes should be checked with WoS' published classification structure.

Table 3: Changes in the sc_traditional discipline classification structure between the previous and current databases

Classification	Previous pubs	Current pubs
----------------	---------------	--------------

Figure 13 shows the number of publications assigned to specific sc_traditional disciplines known to have changed in recent versions of the database.

Figure 13: Time-series of sc_traditional disciplines previously observed to have changed.

Disciplines: Changes in articles and reviews by discipline

This section identifies the disciplines that had a substantial change in the number of publications assigned to them between the latest years in each database. Changes in counts of publications per discipline may reflect changes in the journals indexed, the classification structure, and any potential processing issues. As such, any large changes shown here may be worth examining.

We show in Figure 14 the 40 disciplines with the highest percentage increases and decreases in publication counts between 2022 in wos_b_202304 and 2023 in wos_b_202404. The number shown next to each bar is the numerical change in publication counts. We have used whole counting. Disciplines previously identified as being new or removed have not been included here.

Figure 14: The 40 disciplines with the highest percentage change in publication counts between 2022 in wos_b_202304 and 2023 in wos_b_202404, with numerical difference in counts.

Disciplines: Percentage of publications not assigned to a discipline

Figure 15 shows the percentage of publications in each database that were not assigned to a discipline over the previous 11 years. Complete assignment of publications to disciplines is important as citation-based indicators typically use field-normalisation to account for differences in citation practices between disciplines. As such, items missing discipline information are excluded from such analyses and so large percentages of, or large changes in, unclassified items should be investigated.

Figure 15: The percentage of publications in each database that do not have a discipline classification.

Metadata: Changes in pubyear, doctype, pubtype and items removed

This section details the number of items for which changes were made to key metadata in the latest iteration of the database or the items were removed. We look at changes in the recorded publication year, document type and publication type as these three variables are typically the key inclusion criteria for bibliometric analyses. We also examine the number of items that were present in the wos_b_202304 database but not in the wos_b_202404 database (removed items), and items present in the wos_b_202404 database but not in the wos_b_202304 database (added items). A change in metadata for a large number of items may be problematic, particularly if the changes are not randomly distributed, such as adjustments having been made to items from a particular journal or set of publications, which may affect counts and indicators for specific entities. Some changes can be expected as the database provider updates or corrects items. However, changes to or removal of a large number of items may require investigation. Notably, the documents examined are not restricted to articles and reviews, but any document type.

We identified changes in the metadata of in-scope items by first matching items between the wos_b_202304 and wos_b_202404 databases using the item_id identifier and then calculating the number of items that were added, removed, or had different metadata. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: The number of items with changes in metadata between wos_b_202304 and wos_b_202404.

Crrnt year	Prvs year	Diff. year	Diff. src type	Diff. doc type	Added	Removed
2017	2017	0	0	780	0	0
2017	2018	19	0	0	0	0
2017		0	0	0	715	0
2018	2018	0	0	1010	0	0
2018	2019	59	0	0	0	0
2018		0	0	0	2311	0
2019	2018	11	0	0	0	0
2019	2019	0	0	2187	0	0
2019	2020	3	0	3	0	0
2019	2022	1	0	1	0	0
2019		0	0	0	2024	0
2020	2019	25	0	10	0	0
2020	2020	0	1	2611	0	0
2020	2021	13	0	3	0	0
2020	2022	11	0	8	0	0
2020		0	0	0	5163	0
2021	2019	24	0	23	0	0
2021	2020	180	0	65	0	0
2021	2021	0	0	5557	0	0
2021	2022	328	0	57	0	0
2021		0	0	0	17371	0
2022	2018	8	0	1	0	0
2022	2019	5	0	2	0	0
2022	2020	106	0	42	0	0
2022	2021	1921	0	1763	0	0
2022	2022	0	561	17115	0	0
2022		0	0	0	95415	0
2023	2017	1	0	1	0	0
2023	2018	2	0	2	0	0
2023	2019	305	0	301	0	0
2023	2020	1505	0	1486	0	0
2023	2021	17507	0	17496	0	0
2023	2022	114801	0	113901	0	0
2023		0	0	0	2874469	0
	2017	0	0	0	0	356
	2018	0	0	0	0	10
	2019	0	0	0	0	312
	2020	0	0	0	0	534
	2021	0	0	0	0	2294
	2022	0	0	0	0	19890

Metadata: Publications from each index

The WoS database is comprised of several indices. The KB contract with Clarivate Analytics specifies that we receive data from the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI), Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI), and the Arts and Humanities Citation Index (AHCI). The other indices are the Book Citation Index (Science, BSCI), Conference Proceedings Citation Index (Science, ISTP), Conference Proceedings Citation Index (Social Sciences & Humanities, ISSHP), Current Chemical Reactions (CCR), Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI), and Index Chemicus (IC). The inclusion of items from other indices can be problematic as these items may fundamentally differ from those in the three core indices in, for instance, the countries of their authors or publishing journals, which can influence citation-based indicators. As such, we examine in Figure 16 the number of articles and reviews in each index in the `wos_b_202304` and `wos_b_202404` databases between 2013 and 2023.

Figure 16: The number of articles and reviews in each WoS index by database over time.

Metadata: Missing metadata variables

Figure 17 shows the annual percentage of publications in each database that are missing particular metadata, including page numbers, journal issue and volume information, DOIs, titles, references, abstracts, and keywords. We could reasonably expect improvements over time in missing metadata, such as for DOIs through increasing uptake of this identifier, however increasing missing metadata should be investigated. Empty graphs indicate there were no items missing this metadata.

Figure 17: The percentage of items with missing metadata over time by database.

Institution and country data: Number of articles and reviews with missing data

Bibliometric analyses often examine indicators at the level of institutions or countries. Further, fractional counting can be applied based on institutions, with articles apportioned according to authors' affiliations. It is imperative for accurate indicators that most, if not all, items have institution and country data, as missing information removes otherwise valid items from analyses.

The items table of the KB databases holds a record of all available items, while the associated data about authors' affiliations are held, in part, in the items_affiliations tables. We have operationalised missing institution information here as publications that appear in the items table but have no corresponding information in the items_affiliation tables. We present in the top panel of Figure 18 the number of items in each database between 2013 and 2023 with no institution information. Additionally, items can have institution information but no country code – from which country counts are derived – and these are shown in the bottom panel of Figure 18. Large disparities between the databases or substantial increases in missing information should be investigated.

Figure 18: The number of items with missing institution information (top) and the additional items that have institution information but no country code (bottom) over time by database.

Author-institution links: Percentage complete by Research Area and discipline

Similarly to ensuring that all or most items have institution and country information, it is important for allocating publications to entities that authors' affiliations with institutions have been assigned for the majority, or ideally all, items. As such, we examine here the percentage of items in each sc_traditional discipline with complete links between authors and institutions.

In Figure 19, we see in the left panel the percentage of complete links for 2022 data in both the previous and current databases, highlighting any retroactive changes that may have been made in the current database. In the right panel is again the percentage of complete links made in 2022 in the wos_b_202304, now compared with the 2023 in the wos_b_202404, indicating potential changes between the latest year in each database.

Figure 19: The percentage of complete author-institution links by disciplines.

Table 5 shows the outlying disciplines observable in the right panel of Figure 19 that changed by more than 7 percentage points in the percentage of complete author-institution links.

Table 5: Disciplines that changed by more than 7 percentage points in missing links between 2021 in wos_b_202304 and 2022 in wos_b_202404.

Discipline	Prvs %	Crrnt %	Prvs no.	Crrnt no.	Change
Poetry	48.1	63.6	38	63	-15.54
Literature, African, Australian, Canadian	65.1	75.8	95	91	-10.76
Literature, British Isles	75.3	82.4	247	262	-7.09
Dance	60.8	51.7	127	107	9.08

To provide context to the percentage of complete links observed in the most recent years, in Figure 20 we present the percentage of complete links made between authors and affiliations in each Research Area over the last decade in both databases, plus 2023 in wos_b_202404. Substantial changes between years or differences between the databases may require investigation of the cause.

Figure 20: The annual percentage of complete author-institution links by Research Area and database.

German institutions: German publications missing from KB institution coding

In Figure 21 we show the annual percentage of German publications, i.e. those where the German indicator is TRUE, that were not assigned a KB institution code through the institution coding process. Increases over time may be due to the foundation of new institutions that have not yet been integrated into the coding process. However, publications without KB institutions are typically excluded from sector-level analyses, so it is important to understand the extent of missing institution information.

Figure 21: The percentage of German publications in each database that are missing a KB institution.

German institutions: Changes in whole counts of articles and reviews

This section compares changes in the number of articles and reviews published by German institutions between the latest years available in each database. These tables can assist in identifying institutions for which substantial numbers of publications have been added, removed or otherwise changed in the latest database. They can also aid in assessing the degree of change in publication numbers for larger institutions, which may require further examination if considered unusual or excessive.

Table 6 presents potentially new institutions – these had no publications in 2022 in the wos_b_202304 database but more than five publications in 2023 in the wos_b_202404 database. Conversely, Table 7 shows the institutions that had at least five publications in 2022 in the wos_b_202304 database but no publications recorded in 2023 in the wos_b_202404 database. We also highlight in Tables 8 and 9 the larger institutions (with at least 20 publications) that had a change in publication counts of more than 40% between 2022 and 2023 in the wos_b_202304 and wos_b_202404 databases.

Table 6: Institutions with more than 5 publications in 2023 in wos_b_202404 that had no publications in 2022 in wos_b_202304.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs
813	Europäisches Laboratorium für Molekularb	0	411
5829	Fakultät für Gesundheitswissenschaften -	0	220

4426	Exzellenzcluster ORIGINS	0	210
6136	Exzellenzcluster NeuroCure	0	146
5060	Göttingen Campus	0	137
6260	ct.qmat - Complexity and Topology in Qua	0	137
6152	Landschaftsverband Westfalen-Lippe (LWL)	0	107
6154	Bayerisches Polymerinstitut	0	99
6250	Excellence Cluster Cardio-Pulmonary Inst	0	88
3865	RZPD Deutsches Ressourcenzentrum für Gen	0	86
4430	Center for Free-Electron Laser Science	0	85
2116	Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrtmedizin d	0	84
6054	Hamburger Institut für Sozialforschung	0	84
6155	Bayerische Zentrum für Krebsforschung (B	0	79
5879	HMU Health and Medical University Potsda	0	76
6036	AbbVie Deutschland GmbH & Co. KG	0	74
6117	TWINCORE Zentrum für Experimentelle und	0	73
5942	Senckenberg Centre for Human Evolution a	0	70
5894	Hochschule Weihenstephan-Triesdorf	0	66
5957	European Reference Network for Rare Dise	0	65
2827	Klinikum Augsburg	0	64
6005	Facility for Antiproton and Ion Research	0	61
6191	Zentrum für Individualisierte Infektions	0	60
6128	Exzellenzcluster Cellular Stress Respons	0	59
250	Europäische Kommission	0	54
1502	E.ON	0	52
6221	Global Labor Organization (GLO) gGmbH	0	51
817	Deutsches Jugendinstitut e.V. (DJI)	0	50
892	NMI Naturwissenschaftliches und Medizini	0	49
240	United Nations University	0	48
5857	Berliner Hochschule für Technik (BHT)	0	47
798	Institut für medizinischen Arbeits- und	0	44
5941	Bayerische Staatssammlung für Paläontolo	0	44
1029	Max-Planck-Institut zur Erforschung von	0	43
4748	IU Internationale Hochschule GmbH	0	43
5958	Münchener Rückversicherungs-Gesellschaft	0	43
6208	Institute for Lung Health (ILH)	0	43
5928	Zentrum für angewandte Raumfahrttechnolo	0	42
6203	Munich Center for Machine Learning	0	39
4192	Institut für Transfusionsmedizin und Imm	0	38
5837	Zentrum für Individualisierte Infektiosm	0	37
6215	Berlin Institute for the Foundations of	0	37
5885	Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften	0	33
5899	Ostfalia Hochschule für angewandte Wisse	0	33
6238	Sozialstiftung Bamberg	0	33

1096	European Space Agency	0	32
6012	Bonn-Aachen International Center for Inf	0	32
5897	Katholische Hochschule für Sozialwesen B	0	30
6195	Nokia Deutschland	0	30
5906	Technische Hochschule Aschaffenburg	0	29
6026	European Astronaut Center (EAC)	0	29
6034	Daiichi Sankyo Europe GmbH	0	29
5914	Max Planck School Matter to Life	0	28
920	Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Verbrauc	0	27
5779	Deutsches Zentrum für Integrations- und	0	27
5975	European Virus Bioinformatics Center	0	27
5838	Nationalpark Berchtesgaden	0	26
5886	Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	0	25
5960	BARMER	0	25
6169	Wissenschaftliches Institut der AOK (WId	0	25
6262	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather	0	25
6225	Nuvisan GmbH	0	24
1445	Institut für Chemo- und Biosensorik (ICB	0	23
5999	Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt (LfU)	0	23
6159	SPORTHOPAEDICUM STRAUBING – BERLIN – REG	0	23
6210	Sammelkategorie Vereine, Stiftungen	0	23
841	Bundesamt für Naturschutz (BfN)	0	22
930	Leibniz-Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe (0	21
1126	Fraunhofer-Institutszentrum Schloss Birl	0	21
1569	Bruker BioSpin GmbH	0	21
5913	Max Planck School of Cognition	0	21
6009	AWMF (Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Wissenscha	0	21
6018	Deutscher Verein des Gas- und Wasserfach	0	21
6023	Dresdner Grundwasserforschungszentrum (D	0	21
6123	IDeA-Zentrum	0	21
5903	SRH Berlin University of Applied Science	0	20
6017	Curt-Engelhorn-Zentrum Archäometrie gGmb	0	20
6045	Giersch Science Center (GSC)	0	20
6187	Asklepios Medical School GmbH	0	20
6219	IFN Schönow e.V.	0	20
696	KfH Kuratorium für Dialyse und Nierentra	0	19
1292	Henkel AG & Co KGaA	0	19
5812	Hochschule für Musik und Theater Hamburg	0	19
5863	Deutsche Hochschule für Prävention und G	0	19
5907	Technische Hochschule Ulm (THU)	0	19
6027	European Forest Institute (EFI) - Stando	0	19
6137	Schaeffler Technologies AG & Co. KG	0	19
6143	Privatpraxis Prof. Jonas und Dr. Panda-J	0	19

6164	Krebsregister Saarland	0	19
834	Bundesinstitut für Berufsbildung (BIBB)	0	18
4694	Zentralinstitut für die kassenärztliche	0	18
5915	Max Planck School of Photonics	0	18
5950	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale	0	18
6067	Institute for Integrated Management of M	0	18
702	ISEG Institut für Sozialmedizin, Epidemi	0	17
1384	KWS Saat AG	0	17
1410	Institut für Sozialmedizin, Epidemiologi	0	17
1442	IDEXX GmbH	0	17
5887	Hochschule für Forstwirtschaft Rottenbur	0	17
5891	Hochschule Hof	0	17
1457	Heraeus Holding GmbH	0	16
4404	Institut für sozial-ökologische Forschung	0	16
5900	PFH Private Hochschule Göttingen	0	16
5938	Porsche AG	0	16
5954	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Urologie e.V.	0	16
5832	Global Climate Forum e.V. (GCF)	0	15
5893	Hochschule Stralsund	0	15
6002	Deutsche Institute für Textil- und Faser	0	15
5972	Lead Discovery Center GmbH	0	14
6079	Institut für Angewandte Trainingswissens	0	14
6144	Cluster of Excellence RESOLV	0	14
6156	Geoverbund ABC/J	0	14
6229	Medicover GmbH	0	14
500	Bezirkskrankenhaus Augsburg Klinik für P	0	13
5865	DIPLOMA Hochschule	0	13
5948	Infinera Deutschland GmbH	0	13
6189	Deutsche Diabetes Stiftung	0	13
6251	WIG2 GmbH	0	13
6259	Deutsches Meeresmuseum - Museum für Meer	0	13
832	Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie	0	12
5388	Linde AG	0	12
5845	von Hoerner & Sulger GmbH	0	12
5854	Akkon-Hochschule für Humanwissenschaften	0	12
5855	APOLLON Hochschule der Gesundheitswirtsc	0	12
5880	Hochschule der Bundesagentur für Arbeit	0	12
5883	Hochschule des Bundes für öffentliche Ve	0	12
6087	Institut für Hygiene und Umwelt	0	12
6121	Zentrum für Osteuropa- und International	0	12
6153	UKM Marienhospital Steinfurt GmbH	0	12
6194	Evangelisches Klinikum Bethel gGmbH	0	12
6246	Experimental Pharmacology & Oncology Ber	0	12

6248	Zalando SE	0	12
751	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Anästhesiologi	0	11
1121	Fraunhofer-Zentrum für Internationales M	0	11
4534	Institut für Diabetes-Technologie an der	0	11
5781	DEval - Deutsches Evaluierungsinstitut d	0	11
5840	Bonn International Centre for Conflict S	0	11
5844	Klinikum St. Marien Amberg	0	11
5952	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Gastroenterolo	0	11
5979	Alexander von Humboldt-Stiftung	0	11
6112	Stiftung Institut für Herzinfarktforschu	0	11
6163	Landeskrebsregister NRW gGmbH	0	11
208	Institut für Lebensmittel- und Umweltfor	0	10
881	Stiftung Schleswig-Holsteinische Landesm	0	10
4425	Rostocker Zentrum zur Erforschung des De	0	10
5389	Framatome GmbH	0	10
5849	Centrum für Hämatologie und Onkologie Be	0	10
5890	Hochschule für Wirtschaft und Gesellscha	0	10
6099	Institut für Therapie- und Gesundheitsfo	0	10
6111	Statistisches Bundesamt	0	10
6161	Science-Consulting in Diabetes GmbH	0	10
6213	CUTANEON - Skin & Hair Innovations GmbH	0	10
6228	ADAMA Deutschland GmbH	0	10
6237	StatConsult Gesellschaft für klinische u	0	10
6243	MVZ genetikum® GmbH	0	10
6253	spectrumK GmbH	0	10
6272	IKF Pneumologie GmbH & Co. KG - Institut	0	10
858	Bundesamt für Migration und Flüchtlinge	0	9
959	Hochschule für Politik München (HfP)	0	9
4491	Faserinstitut Bremen e.V. (FIBRE)	0	9
4695	Zentrum für Pränataldiagnostik und Human	0	9
5916	Landesamt für Bergbau, Energie und Geolo	0	9
6091	Institut für Marine Biotechnologie e.V.	0	9
6102	Retinologische Gesellschaft e. V.	0	9
6167	Bavarian Nordic GmbH	0	9
6182	VODAFONE Deutschland	0	9
6200	Labor Dr. Wisplinghoff	0	9
335	St. Marien-Hospitals Mülheim an der Ruhr	0	8
848	Bundesagentur für Arbeit	0	8
889	Osteuropa-Institut (OEI)	0	8
949	Institut für Biotechnologie und Wirkstof	0	8
5892	Hochschule Macromedia	0	8
5904	SRH Fernhochschule Riedlingen	0	8
5955	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Allgemein- und	0	8

5970	Energie Campus Nürnberg	0	8
6001	Bayerisches Zentrum für Angewandte Energ	0	8
6086	Institut für Holztechnologie Dresden gGm	0	8
6104	Landesamt für Denkmalpflege und Archäolo	0	8
6119	Landesbetrieb Hessisches Landeslabor	0	8
6134	glyXera GmbH	0	8
6183	Heidelberg Materials AG	0	8
6230	Charles River Deutschland	0	8
6233	Signatope GmbH	0	8
6249	Kompetenznetz Vorhofflimmern e.V.	0	8
6261	Radiologische Allianz eGbR	0	8
6265	St. Josef-Stift Sendenhorst	0	8
908	Landeslabor Berlin-Brandenburg	0	7
1243	SMS group GmbH	0	7
1249	Shimadzu Europa GmbH	0	7
2691	Bundesministerium für Digitales und Verk	0	7
4117	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung de	0	7
5816	Staatliche Akademie der Bildenden Künste	0	7
5839	Berlin Center for Genomics in Biodiversi	0	7
5841	MBN Research Center gGmbH	0	7
5843	Radiometer Physics GmbH	0	7
5896	Karlshochschule International University	0	7
5920	Neue Materialien Bayreuth GmbH	0	7
5946	Kriminologische Zentralstelle e.V. (Krim	0	7
5951	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Rheumatologie	0	7
5968	PROTEROS BIOSTRUCTURES GMBH	0	7
5993	Neurologisches Rehabilitationszentrum Go	0	7
5995	Bauhaus Luftfahrt e.V.	0	7
6033	BioSolveIT GmbH	0	7
6074	Reiner Lemoine Institut gGmbH	0	7
6097	Institut für Nanophotonik Göttingen e.V.	0	7
6124	AVL Deutschland Netzwerk	0	7
6149	AVL Deutschland GmbH	0	7
6162	Heidelberg Engineering GmbH	0	7
6204	ClinCompetence Cologne GmbH	0	7
6245	Epilepsiezentrum Kleinwachau gemeinnützi	0	7
6254	Ministerium für Ländlichen Raum und Verb	0	7
527	Klinikum Starnberg Akademisches Lehrkran	0	6
538	Marienhospital Aachen	0	6
689	Parmenides Foundation	0	6
744	DRF Stiftung Luftrettung gemeinnützige A	0	6
810	Bundesforschungsanstalt für Landwirtscha	0	6
967	Generaldirektion Kulturelles Erbe Rheinl	0	6

2669	ONKOLOGIKUM Frankfurt am Museumsufer	0	6
3820	Zentrum für Epidemiologie & Gesundheitsf	0	6
4745	Hochschule für Musik Detmold	0	6
5539	Deutsche Hochschule der Polizei	0	6
5707	Evangelische Hochschule Rheinland-Westfa	0	6
5790	Hochschule für Bildende Künste Dresden	0	6
5850	Deutsche Rheuma-Liga Bundesverband e.V.	0	6
5868	Evangelische Hochschule Dresden	0	6
5909	Touro College Berlin	0	6
5912	European Hidradenitis Suppurativa Founda	0	6
5929	Zentrum für Mechatronik und Automatisier	0	6
6032	CAPNETZ Stiftung	0	6
6037	Mammazentrum Hamburg	0	6
6103	Vector Consulting Services (VCS) GmbH	0	6
6127	THE CROP TRUST	0	6
6165	Hamburgisches Krebsregister	0	6
6175	TOMTEC Imaging Systems GmbH	0	6
6178	Brainlab AG	0	6
6197	Shell Deutschland GmbH	0	6
6231	Raith GmbH	0	6
6275	BioTeSys GmbH	0	6

Table 7: Institutions with no publications in 2023 in wos_b_202404 that had more than 5 publications in 2022 in wos_b_202304.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs
4737	Institute for Advanced Sustainability St	101	0
5611	Helmholtz-Institut für Metabolismus-, Ad	61	0
5483	Fraunhofer-Institut für Energiewirtschaft	29	0
1328	Nokia Siemens Networks GmbH & Co. KG	22	0
3929	Epidemiologisches Krebsregister Saarland	20	0
5609	Deutsche Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY	12	0
1264	Sankyo Europe GMBH	8	0
4448	Institut für Mechatronik e.V.	6	0
5410	Werlhof-Institut MVZ	6	0
5753	Hochschule für Wirtschaft und Umwelt Nür	6	0

Table 8: Institutions with more than 20 publications in 2022 in wos_b_202304 that increased in publication counts by over 40% in 2023 in wos_b_202404.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs	Perc. diff.
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192	Zentralinstitut für Seelische Gesundheit	26	310	1092.3
610	Hochschule Ostwestfalen-Lippe	22	173	686.4
5211	Max-Planck-Institut für Biologie	31	180	480.6
4400	Centrum für Integrierte Onkologie Köln B	64	307	379.7
211	Senckenberg Museum für Naturkunde Görlitz	34	113	232.4
587	Fachhochschule Lübeck	27	88	225.9
1146	Fraunhofer-Institut für Produktionstechn	47	125	166.0
1572	Bruker Corporation	31	78	151.6
662	Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	30	71	136.7
5373	LungenClinic Grosshansdorf - Akademische	22	52	136.4
1021	Max-Planck-Institut für Stoffwechselfors	32	73	128.1
545	Hochschule Worms, University of Applied	35	76	117.1
1090	Max-Planck-Institut für Astrophysik	331	712	115.1
785	Umweltbundesamt	61	130	113.1
396	HELIOS Kliniken GmbH	442	889	101.1
1031	Max-Planck-Institut für Bildungsforschun	231	462	100.0
5736	BioNTech SE	23	44	91.3
573	Technische Hochschule Nürnberg Georg Sim	21	40	90.5
3750	Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	33	62	87.9
1035	Max-Planck-Institut für molekulare Genet	93	174	87.1
179	ESCP Europe Berlin Campus	24	44	83.3
514	Deutsches Herzzentrum Berlin	198	363	83.3
621	Hochschule Hannover	34	60	76.5
5616	Leibniz-Institut zur Analyse des Biodive	134	236	76.1
5741	Comprehensive Cancer Center Erlangen-EMN	114	200	75.4
314	Klinikum Osnabrück GmbH	24	42	75.0
1866	Sana Klinikum Lichtenberg, Berlin	27	47	74.1
1076	Max-Planck-Institut für Entwicklungsbiol	61	104	70.5
295	Rhön-Klinikum AG	33	56	69.7
607	Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft de	23	39	69.6
1481	Fresenius SE & Co. KGaA	23	39	69.6
50	Leibniz-Institut für Experimentelle Viro	58	97	67.2
4625	Institut für Molekulare Biologie gGmbH	70	117	67.1
5368	Translational Lung Research Center Heide	91	151	65.9
5140	Restkategorie Universitätskliniken Münch	127	206	62.2
745	Deutsches Institut für Lebensmitteltechn	55	89	61.8
732	Frankfurt Institute for Advanced Studies	160	257	60.6
627	Hochschule Fresenius	28	44	57.1
584	Hochschule Mannheim	46	72	56.5
904	Bayerische Landesanstalt für Wald und Fo	27	42	55.6
327	Berufsgenossenschaftliche Unfallklinik M	41	63	53.7
255	St. Josefs-Hospital Wiesbaden	25	38	52.0
5348	Deutsches Zentrum für Lungenforschung	538	807	50.0

835	Bundesinstitut für Bevölkerungsforschung	33	49	48.5
515	St. Hedwig-Krankenhaus Berlin	30	44	46.7
195	Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde Stuttg	94	137	45.7
296	Rheumazentrum Ruhrgebiet St. Josefs-Kran	47	68	44.7
1019	Max-Planck-Institut für Physik (Werner-H	260	376	44.6
856	Bundesanstalt für Arbeitsschutz und Arbe	34	49	44.1
562	Ostbayerische Technische Hochschule Rege	55	79	43.6
386	Westpfalz-Klinikum GmbH	23	33	43.5
598	Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	30	43	43.3
1147	Fraunhofer-Institut für Angewandte Optik	72	102	41.7
561	Hochschule RheinMain, RheinMain Universi	29	41	41.4

Table 9: Institutions with more than 20 publications in 2022 in wos_b_202304 that decreased in publication counts by over 40% in 2023 in wos_b_202404.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs	Perc. diff.
821	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	44	26	-40.9
3814	Wissenschaftskolleg zu Berlin	38	22	-42.1
1152	Fraunhofer-Institut für Lasertechnik (IL	77	43	-44.2
1041	Max-Planck-Institut für Mikrostrukturphy	170	93	-45.3
83	Universität Vechta	76	40	-47.4
1058	Max-Planck-Institut für Infektionsbiolog	67	34	-49.3
5569	Leipzig Heart Institute GmbH	59	29	-50.8
1022	Max-Planck-Institut für Neurobiologie	119	53	-55.5
1134	Fraunhofer-Institut für Toxikologie und	215	84	-60.9
1075	Max-Planck-Institut für Geoanthropologie	159	53	-66.7
4429	Restkategorie Fachhochschulen	125	23	-81.6

Authors: Median number of authors by Research Area and discipline

The median number of authors on a paper can be informative about patterns of collaboration and their potential implications for fractional counting. For instance, increasing levels of inter-sector or international collaboration could result in decreased publication counts for individual sectors or countries when using fractional counting. As such, understanding changes in authorship patterns can provide some insight into potential macro-level changes for entities.

We show in the left panel of Figure 22 the median number of authors per sc_traditional discipline in 2022 in both databases, and in the right panel the median number of authors per discipline in 2022 in the wos_b_202304 database compared to 2023 in the wos_b_202404 database.

While little change is expected to be seen in the left-hand panel of Figure 22 as the number of authors on a paper is unlikely to change between databases, differences in the right-hand panel indicate potential changes in disciplines' collaboration patterns. Disciplines for which the median number of authors changed by more than 1, based on the right-hand panel of Figure 22, are shown in Table 10.

Figure 22: Median number of authors per discipline between databases, where colour denotes the number of disciplines with this combination of median authors.

Table 10: Disciplines where the median number of authors changed by more than 1 between 2022 in wos_b_202304 and 2023 in wos_b_202404.

Discipline	Previous median authors	Current median authors	Diff.
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Source items: Percentage by Research Area and discipline

Source items refer to whether the publications on the reference list of an indexed publication are also indexed in the database, as opposed to non-source items that are not indexed. Only source items are included in citation counts and so understanding the percentage of items cited that are also source can give an indication of the depth of WoS' coverage of a discipline. That is, if a large number of indexed items' sources are not indexed, the reverse is also likely true and a large number of citations of indexed items are also missing, which has the effect of reducing citation counts for disciplines with lower coverage, such as the arts and humanities.

The percentage of references that are source items is expected to increase over time as the database provider continues to index journals and makes efforts to improve coverage of journals from disciplines with known low coverage. The percentage is not likely to ever reach 100% however, as authors will continue to cite items outside of the scope or coverage of WoS.

We show in the left-hand panel of Figure 23 the percentage of references that are source items per sc_traditional discipline in 2022 in both databases, and in the right-hand panel the percentage of references that are source items per discipline in 2022 in the wos_b_202304 database compared to 2023 in the wos_b_202404 database.

It is in the right-hand panel that the effect of recently indexed journals may become apparent, where an increase in the percentage of source items may be seen if the journal is often cited within a discipline. The disciplines with a change in the percentage of indexed references of more than five percentage points between databases, based on the right-hand panel of Figure 23, are shown in Table 11. Longer term trends can be seen in Figure 24 where we present the percentage of reference that are source items per Research Area over the last ten common years of both databases.

Figure 23: The percentage of cited items that are source items per sc_traditional discipline by database, where colour denotes the number of disciplines with this combination of source references.

Figure 24: The percentage of references that are source items by Research Area and database over time.

Table 11: Disciplines where the percentage of indexed references changed by 3 or more percentage points between 2022 in wos_b_202304 and 2023 in wos_b_202404.

Discipline	Prvs % source	Crrnt % source	Change
Humanities, Multidisciplinary	25.4	31.4	6.0
Architecture	30.1	33.7	3.6
Nuclear Science & Technology	73.6	69.3	-4.3